

Appendix A: Interview Outline

- What is the reason for the DH Project in your library?
- Where does the funding for the ** DH project in your library come from?
- What tools did you use to develop these DH projects?
- Where does the data for the DH project come from?
- How do you do DH projects?
- Does the DH project work with other structures or experts?
- Is your library's DH project related to other DH projects?
- What is the purpose of the DH project?
- How do users participate in or use the results of these data humanities projects?
- What problems do you think are in the process of implementing the DH project?
- What do you think are the core difficulties in implementing DH projects?
- What do you think is the reason why DH projects are difficult to implement?
- How do you think the DH project should develop?
- What DH projects will your library plan to make in the future?